

THERMALLY ASSISTED PEELING AS A HIGH-QUALITY DISASSEMBLY PROCESS FOR THERMOPLASTIC TAPE WOUND COMPOSITES

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Goal

Materials and Methods

Challenges

Results

Optical inspection

Tensile strength of the recovered tapes

Micrographs

Observations

- **Tape tensile strength have been preserved** (75 % of the initial value for CF-PA6 and more than 85 % for CF-PPS) through peeling-based disassembly.
- **High horizontal forces are favorable to reduce fiber kinking** during mandrel peeling disassembly.
- **Negative temperatures** induce a more brittle matrix behavior and help to **preserve tape tensile properties**.
- **Peeling-based disassembly enables to recover, in one single process step, tapes with equivalent or better mechanical properties** than the ones obtained with laborious recycling processes based on staple fiber processing.
- **Crack propagation occurs more preferably in fiber rich (intralaminar) areas** than in matrix-rich (interlaminar) areas.

Conclusions

Thermally assisted peeling-based disassembly is a promising approach to recover preserved thermoplastic tapes from wound structures.

Ensuring process robustness requires to control crack propagation independently of the variability of the microstructure.

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